

Using Claude 3.7 Sonnet + Project to Build A University Archives Metadata Management System

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Request. Implement. Troubleshoot. Repeat.

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Poster images created with Canva (<https://canva.com>).

Inspiration

This project was inspired by the work of Hudhayfa Nazoordeen, a 20-year-old student at the University of Waterloo who built a proof-of-concept nuclear fusor in his bedroom. Nazoordeen's post describing the project stated that he had "zero hardware experience," his secret of success was "Claude Sonnet 3.5 + Project." Our project challenge, an order of magnitude less ambitious, is to build a proof-of-concept, functional, and integrated University Archives Metadata Management System (UAMMS). As AI tools increase in capability, it is valuable to investigate how far a traditional archivist with limited development experience can go in building a comprehensive metadata management service. Additionally, it has been a valuable learning experience in the strengths and weaknesses of the current generation of AI tools.

AI-Assisted Development Strategy

- Claude + Project
 - Key feature - project documentation repository - 200,000-word capacity
- Preconditioning
 - Novice-level explanations
 - Powershell syntax
 - Proof of concept project - LIMIT FUNCTIONALITY

Project Requirements

- Support the Dublin Core (DC) metadata schema
- Support the creation of new metadata records
- Support updating existing metadata records
- Support import and export using Excel and XML

Implementation

The UAMMS sandbox achieved remarkable development speed, progressing from initial concept to a working database with a web interface in under 5 hours of active development on the first day. Key insights from the development and implementation process:

- **Rapid initial development**
- **Metadata normalization challenges**
- **Steep API integration learning curve**
- **Enhanced deployment speed**
- **Persistent realignment of AI code is required**

Technical Architecture

- **Front-end: HTML, CSS, JavaScript with Bootstrap for responsive design**
- **Backend: Python Flask web application**
- **Database: SQLite with SQL Alchemy ORM**
- **API: RESTful API for integrations**

We focused on a simple approach and a standard set of prerequisites to support scaling up the UAMMS once the proof of concept build was stable. Claude generated the code base directory as the hub for all application and user interface functionality. The code is publicly available on GitHub. (<https://github.com/eamonsmallwood/UAMMS>).

Results and Next Steps

Positive:

- **Rapid code development and deployment**
- **Quick remediation of simple code errors**
- **Code development crash course**

Negative:

- **AI code frequently beyond scope of the request**
- **Low continuity of AI code**
- **AI code is challenging to maintain and update**

Next Steps:

- **Stable deployment of UAMMS**
- **Continued integration and fine-tuning**

Prompt Samples

```
export-5-11-03-2025-10-27-25.json
403 lines
JSON
```

ES I need to normalize the metadata in UAMMS with Libnova. I am uploading our main metadata schema in Libnova.

ES just to confirm, I add these changes to the end of the get_all_libnova_metadata.py script?

No, these changes should be integrated into the existing script, not added to the end. Let me clarify where each of the modifications should go:

ES Okay. Now I want to try and get all Libnova object metadata. Here are the code snippets they have in their documentation: conditions object - body

```
{
  "conditions": [
    {
      "column": "value"
    },
    {
      "column": {
        "operator": "Like | starts_with | ends_with | eq | leq | in | not_in | gt | lt | gte | lte",
        "value": "value"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

ES I am getting this error: (venv) PS C:\Projects\metadata-management-poc-311(function> python normalize_metadata.py "export-5-11-03-2025_10-27-25.json" Error loading Libnova schema: [Errno 2] No such file or directory: 'export-5-11-03-2025_10-27-25.json' Failed to load Libnova schema

```
function(normalize_metadata) {
  import json
  import argparse
  from datetime import datetime
  def load_schema(schema_path):
    PASTED
  }
}
```

ES Here is the contents of normalize_metadata.py:

Based on the script, the issue is that Python can't find the app module. Here are a few solutions:

ES how do i check that these fields were added to the database?

There are a few ways to verify the newly added fields in the database:

1. Using the view_data.py script we saw earlier:

ES Ah, nevermind. I can see the fields have been added to the schema @ <http://localhost:5000/schemas/>. I tested the export metadata function @ <http://localhost:5000/import-export/> and it does not include the normalized fields. Let's update the template.

ES it works! Do we need to reintegrate some of the JS code back into the test connection route?

Conclusion

Claude 3.7 Sonnet + Project proved to be an effective method for supporting the development of a metadata management tool with minimal programming experience required. This project demonstrates that the current state of AI-assisted code development is more beneficial for those with limited programming experience. Experienced programmers may find the code generated by current LLMs overly elaborate and requiring many revisions. Claude tended to be unnecessarily verbose when developing product documentation and code. Claude required a persistent stream of limiting prompts to refine the outputs to fit the project scope and requirements. Even as LLMs and other AI tools continue to advance, a human actor must be involved in specifying requirements and evaluating whether the AI outputs meet those requirements.